

Mahasiddhartha

About

- This manual talks about the Great Attainment, the Highest End of Any Being in Any Realm.
- The Great Attainment may be symbolized by Om.

A System of Truths

- 1. Soul and life are inseparable
- 2. Nature of soul is bliss
- 3. This bliss is beyond mind
- 4. It is the bliss of knowing
- 5. Soul and life can be unified in subjective perception
- 6. Meditation is the unification of soul and life
- 7. When meditation becomes natural, it is the Great Attainment
- 8. The system of truths merges in the ocean of truth

A System of Meditation

- Meditation on the system of truths
- Detachment from all states

Advanced Meditation

- 1. It requires harmonization between inner and outer
- 2. It requires renunciation of ambition and pleasure
- 3. With 1. and 2. meditation is made natural

Fruits of the Great Attainment

- The limited frame of man becomes a blessing to all the realms. And he himself the sole, one Consciousness.

Rules for Daily Living

- 1. Daily contemplation on the manual, at every opportunity
- 2. Celibacy
- 3. Service to society in any way
- 4. Reverence to every being as a Mahasidhhaartha